

ENZYMES AS INNOVATION FOR BIOBASED PACKAGING AT THE FOOD VALUE CHAIN

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Abstract: *Despite the ultimate and global goal should be reducing the amount of packaging used and/or substituting the plastic by biobased ones, some goods will require to be packed. For instance, small fruits such as berries have to be sold together, certain fresh products need to be protected with a case to prevent damages, and others need to be packaged to extend their shelf-life and maintain adequate organoleptic properties. For this reason, an outstanding advance in packaging material, with consistent features and appropriate cost-benefit, will lead to a decrease in food waste and less use of plastics, which causes so much damage to the environment. Thinner plastic films and containers contaminated with food usually can't be recycled or used for food contact applications, limiting their reuse. Compostability can be a preferred end of life for such type of packaging. Several commercial materials are available, being polylactic acid one of the most used biopolymers due to their characteristics and price. However, PLA is industrial compostable but not home compostable. In this study, biobased matrices based on PLA and Biodolomer® and an enzymated Master Batch providing enhanced compostable properties to the final packaging, have been used. The enzymated masterbatch can increase the compostability in a 20%-30% (to be labelled as home compostable) together with an increase of compostability of packaging with a thickness above 2 mm.*

Keywords: biodegradability, compostability, enzymated masterbatch, PLA matrix, packaging.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, there are no cost-effective, home-compostable materials with high bio-content rate that complies with food packaging requirements (resistance, transparency, compostability and food safety requirements). 86% of plastics that are used for packaging are bio-based but non-biodegradable, such as bio-based PET. In the case of rigid packaging, according to TÜV Austria database, only 32 rigid packaging products have been certified “OK Compost Home”. For instance, the EU project FRESH developed and upscaled performant cellulose-based trays. Other products include trays made of sugarcane pulp, natural fibres, or paper but none of these solutions combine home-compostability & transparency.

Materials with high PLA content are difficult to process. Their low viscosity and melt strength cause problems during extrusion such as bubble instabilities or excessive neck-in during extrusion. Also, PLAs brittle nature makes it hard to process as thin film and requires blending with other cheaper & less environmental-friendly polymers (Robertson GL, 2012). All those issues impend scaling up and a lot of effort is set towards optimisation of blends and extrusion processes. Also, Biodolomer®, a high-quality mineral filled biomaterial is in a validating phase although is opaque, so it is useful in non transparent applications.

These options present several advantages, including low environmental impact and maintained properties. While both, PLA and Biodolomer, are ready for industrial scale production, very few food packaging applications currently rely on these raw materials. Indeed, it is mostly used in the cosmetic sector or for cups.

Furthermore, the various possible end-of-life for these packaging solutions includes the usual recycling (mechanical and chemical), incineration and composting/biodegradation options. Mechanical recycling and home-compostability of packaging biobased materials are poorly developed in Europe and have limitations for subsequent reuses.

Even if chemical recycling is virtuous for single-layer packaging, recycling in a broader sense is currently not suitable in Europe for multi-layer packaging, which is mostly incinerated or landfilled. Some approaches are available to tackle this challenge but are still at an early stage of industrial development, such as the solvent based CreaSolv® technology or the use of removable barrier layers. In the case of multi-layer packaging, which is widely used in the food sector, the development of compostable solutions, would enable to address this lack of suitable and sustainable end of life options.

In this sense, enzymes can help to manufacture fully biodegradable compostable plastics especially for PLA-based products. It is then of high interest the combination of transparency and home compostability for film products, so the customers can see the product inside but also high thickness packaging (although non transparent) with home compostability features for rigid packaging as trays, as unique selling points which cannot be achieved by any other biopolymer available as of today.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Compostable bioplastics were obtained by mixing selected biopolymers, an enzymatic masterbatch, which is a *compound made with PLA base and protected enzymes to have enough enzymatic activity*, and other additives to improve material final performance in a conventional extrusion compounding process (Coperion ZSK26 co-rotating twin-screw extruder, semi-industrial) at AITIIP facilities (Zaragoza, Spain). The compounded materials were afterwards dried (Mini dryers Moretto X DRY AIR T) to ensure a low water level content that could negatively affect to the product properties.

The compostable materials selected were PLA (Natureplast, France) and Biodolomer (Gaia, Sweden). Films were based on Natureplast PLE 005-A and Biodolomer I for injection moulding. The enzymated masterbatch was added at a 5% for film packaging and at a 10% for rigid packaging (thickness above 2 mm). Due to industrial secret is not possible to indicate the exact percentages used and other additives used.

Table 1. Samples references, description, and main composition.

Reference	Description	Matrix	Enzymated mastebatch
<i>SSTF5-23</i>	<i>Stretch film</i>	<i>PLA</i>	<i>5%</i>
<i>SFSF6-23</i>	<i>Flow pack film</i>	<i>PLA</i>	<i>5%</i>
<i>SRP2-23</i>	<i>Injection moulding</i>	<i>BIODOLOMER</i>	<i>10%</i>

2.2 Production of demonstrators

The materials compounded were transformed into final products films and cosmetic jars, the extrusion blow moulding machine (LABTECH LBM 125, semi-industrial) equipped with a Laboratory Extruder Types LE25-30/C and LE30-30/C Manufactured by: Labtech Engineering Co., Ltd. Was used to obtain the compostable films. Stretch films were produced with different thicknesses

between 15-50 microns and a width of 23 cm, samples for flow pack were produced with thickness between 50-70 microns and width of 31 cm.

The injection moulding machine with an 800 kN clamping force (KraussMaffei 80/380 CX) for processing of thermoplasts, was used enabling fast and cost-effective prototype jars production (Lid: ± 4.3 mm (edge) and ± 5.9 mm (top) – Outer cup: ± 6.3 mm (sidewall), ± 4.9 mm (bottom) – Inner cup: ± 1.0 mm (sidewall), ± 0.9 mm edge and ± 1.0 mm (bottom)). Specimens for mechanical testing were obtained by injection moulding with a JSW 85 EL II electric injection machine (Tokyo, Japan) by following ISO 178 and ISO 527 standards. These were tested and broken samples were used to study the structural properties.

Figure 1. From left to right, extrusion-compounding, film blowing for and injection moulding processes.

2. 3 Characterization Analyses

2. 3. 1 Tensile and Flexural Testing

Mechanical tests were conducted under ambient conditions using a Zwick Roell Z 2.5 (Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany). At least five specimens per material were tested, according to ISO 178 (flexural properties) and ISO 527 1-2 (tensile test) methodology. The distance between the grips was set to 60 mm. The presented values of elasticity modulus (E_t), bend strength (σ_M), and elongation at break (ϵ_b) are an average from at least six replicates from each final material.

2. 3. 2 Home compostability (“OK compost HOME” scheme, developed by TÜV Austria)

The Home compostability is carried on according to the “OK compost HOME” scheme, developed by TÜV Austria, as international recognised Certification Body, taking into account that there is no existing international recognised standard method specifically addressed to the evaluation of the compostability under domestic condition. This scheme defines that the EN 13432 standard is applied at lower temperatures (between 20°C and 30°C) and increased test duration (1 year for biodegradation according to ISO 14855-1 and 6 months for disintegration according to ISO 16929) compared to the industrial compostability.

2. 3. 3 Biodegradability test (ISO 14855-1:2012)

Biodegradation is tested at ambient temperature (between 20°C and 30°C) and maintained below 30°C for all test duration.

The required percentage of biodegradation is the same as specified in EN 13432, namely absolute or relative 90 % (compared with cellulose microcrystalline, as reference material), assessed based on the organic carbon that is transformed into carbon dioxide during the composting process. The period of application for the Home biodegradation test is 12 months as maximum duration.

All constituents and their maximum concentrations as specified on the positive list are regarded as fulfilling the biodegradation requirements as defined by the Certification Body.

2. 3. 4 Disintegration test (ISO 16929:2021)

To determine the degree of disintegration of plastic materials in a pilot-scale aerobic composting test under defined conditions the test method ISO 16929:2021 has been followed. The pilot-scale aerobic composting test simulates as closely as possible a real and complete composting process in composting bins of 200 l. The test item is mixed with the organic fraction of fresh, pretreated municipal solid waste (biowaste) and introduced in an insulated composting bin after which composting spontaneously starts. Like in full-scale composting, inoculation and temperature increase happen spontaneously. The test is considered valid if the maximum temperature during composting is below 30°C. The composting process is directed through air flow and moisture content. The temperature and exhaust gas composition are regularly monitored. The composting process is continued till fully stabilized compost is obtained (6 months). During composting, the contents of the vessels are turned manually, at which time test item is visually evaluated. Disintegration is defined as a size reduction to pieces < 2 mm at the end of the test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1 Mechanical properties

The flexion modulus (E_f), flexion strength (σ_M) and elongation at break (ϵ_b) are presented in table 2. The values are compared to control samples, with the same composition except for the addition of the enzymated masterbatch. In general, the values of the flexural modulus obtained for the resulting materials with addition of enzymated masterbatch significantly decrease in all the samples, flexible and rigid packaging. The values obtained for the bending strength also decreased significantly with the addition of the enzymatic masterbatch and the

elongation at break slightly increases. This means that the materials need less strength to bend and that the elongation is higher until they break, so are more elastic materials compared to the control ones.

Table 2. Flexural results.

Sample	E_f (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)
Control _(SSTF5)	1176 ± 24	33.2 ± 0.3	4.88 ± 0.1
SSTF5	627 ± 17	24.8 ± 0.3	5.51 ± 0.15
Control _(SFSF6)	2633.80 ± 42.45	75.36 ± 0.57	3.79 ± 0.03
SFSF6	1922 ± 160	60.5 ± 1.3	3.85 ± 0.1
Control _(SRP2)	2708 ± 23	55.9 ± 0.7	3.26 ± 0.11
SRP2	2220 ± 33	49.5 ± 0.5	3.46 ± 0.02

Results for tensile modulus (E_t), tensile strength (σ_m) and elongation at break (ϵ_b) are presented in table 3. The values are compared to control samples, with the same composition except for the addition of the enzymated masterbatch. In general, the values of the tensile modulus obtained for the resulting materials with addition of enzymated masterbatch significantly decrease in all the samples, flexible and rigid packaging. The values obtained for the tensile strength also decreased significantly with the addition of the enzymatic masterbatch and the elongation at break slightly increases. This means that the materials are less hard than plain PLA or Biodolomer controls.

Table 3. Tensile test.

Sample	E_t (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_b (%)
Control _(SSTF5)	1378 ± 105	21.4 ± 0.7	3.06 ± 0.17
SSTF5	670 ± 57	11.9 ± 0.5	4.04 ± 0.34
Control _(SFSF6)	2637.80 ± 93	49.84 ± 0.3	3.38 ± 0.23
SFSF6	2041 ± 124	36.4 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.09
Control _(SRP2)	2549 ± 74	31.6 ± 0.6	2.27 ± 0.07
SRP2	2057 ± 89	26.9 ± 0.7	2.37 ± 0.05

3. 2 Biodegradation results

After 85 days of biodegradation, PLA based samples for film packaging with a 5% of enzymatic masterbatch and a thickness of 50 microns, reached between a 40% and a 30% of biodegradation. Although the injected sample has higher thickness (Lid: ± 4.3 mm (edge) and ± 5.9 mm (top) – Outer cup: ± 6.3 mm (sidewall), ± 4.9 mm (bottom) – Inner cup: ± 1.0 mm (sidewall), ± 0.9 mm edge and ± 1.0 mm (bottom)) the Biodolomer based sample and with 10% of enzymatic masterbatch also reached a 30% of biodegradation. In conclusion, the samples are performing well and will reach the biodegradation necessary to comply with the standards.

SAMPLE SSTF5 vs Reference

SFSF6 vs Reference

Sample SRP2 vs Reference

Figure 2. Biodegradation results.

3. 3 Disintegration results.

The disintegration of the cosmetic jar SRP2 proceeded well in spite of the quite high thickness of the product. The different parts (lid, outer cup and inner cup) of the cosmetic jar were evaluated separately for disintegration, but also the complete jar with closed lid was examined to simulate worst-case conditions. Figure 3 shows a visual presentation of the contents of a test bin with SRP2 (last picture), after 85 days of composting. According to previous experiences the cosmetic jar SRP2 has the potential to be compostable at home composting conditions. As for the films, they were produced with PLA matrix and a 5% of enzymatic masterbatch with lower thickness than the injected jars, also have the potential to disintegrate under home composting conditions. In a next step the other requirements of EN 13432 will be examined and the overall home compostability performances will be verified.

SSTF5

SFSF6

SRP2

Figure 3. Home disintegration tests on selected formulations & samples 2023.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study has shown that enzymated masterbatch can be an interesting alternative to enhance biobased and compostable sustainable packaging, contributing to create a new value chain and to the circularity of the European Economy.

The tensile and flexural properties are influenced by this additive and the results shows that the samples are less rigid and more flexible than those made of PLA and Biodolomer without the enzymated masterbatch.

The small variation on the tensile strength confirmed good mixture. The addition does not limit the chain movements in the polymer system and resulted in lower stiffness and higher elongation at break.

Finally, the cosmetic jar and the developed films have the potential to be compostable under HOME composting conditions. After 85 days, the biodegradation reaches a 30%-40% and the disintegration is ongoing as expected even in high thickness samples, thanks to the enzymated masterbatch.

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